

aureus, *Escherichia coli*; *Aerobacter aerogenes* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by the cup plate method⁵. The cups were of 10 mm diameter. Test compounds were dissolved in ethylene glycol or dimethyl formamide and (0.1 ml) placed in each cup. Incubation was at 37° for 4-28 hr. Nitrofurazone, the well-known topical antibacterial agent, was used as standard compound and solvent control was kept. Results obtained are summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

None of the compounds possessed activity against *S.aureus*, *E. coli* and *A. aerogenes* that was significantly better than that of nitrofurazone; some of them even possessed weaker activity. The only noteworthy activity exhibited by these nitrofurans was against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

References

1. W. R. SHERMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 88.
2. H. A. BURCH and W. O. SMITH, *J. Mednl. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 405.
3. M. D. CLOSIER and P. J. ISLIP, *J. Mednl. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 638.
4. B. S. HOLLA and S. Y. AMBEKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16B**, 240.
5. F. F. EBETINO, W. F. CAREY, B. F. STEVENSON, *J. Mednl. Chem.*, 1963, **6**, 633.

Synthesis of Some Aryloxypropionyl Thiosemicarbazides and Related Compounds as Possible Fungicides

(Miss) U. SRIVASTAVA†, R. B. PATHAK*

and

S. C. DAHEL

Chemistry Department, Gorakhpur University,
Gorakhpur-273 001

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDES have been reported to possess significant biological activity^{1,2}. Many triazoles have been known to possess fungicidal³ and pesticidal⁴ action. Several 2,5-disubstituted 1,3,4-thiadiazoles and oxadiazoles have been reported to exhibit antitubercular⁵, antifungal^{5,6} and bactericidal⁷ properties. Keeping these facts in view the title compounds were prepared.

The synthesis of these compounds has been outlined in Scheme 1. The structures were established on the basis of elemental analyses and ir spectra.

† Since deceased.

* Chemistry Department, St. Andrew's College, Gorakhpur-273 001.

Scheme 1

The analytical data of compounds, thus obtained, are given in Tables 1-2.

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	R'	m.p. °C	Yield %
1-(α -Aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides(I) R=2-Cl			
1	H	102	59
2	4-Cl	174	98
3	2-CH ₃	157	53
4	3-OH ₂	161	45
5	4-CH ₃	168	99
3-(α -Aryloxyethyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles(II) R=2-Cl			
6	H	99	96
7	4-Cl	44	98
8	2-CH ₃	147	98
9	3-OH ₂	63	98
10	4-CH ₃	69	62

All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

TABLE-2

Sl. No.	R'	m.p. °C	Yield %
2-Arylamino-5-(α -aryloxyethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles(III) R=2-Cl			
11	H	145	94
12	4-Cl	124	94
13	2-CH ₃	142	89
14	3-OH ₂	155	95
15	4-CH ₃	119	56
2-Arylamino-5-(α -aryloxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles(IV) R=2-Cl			
16	H	181	48
17	4-Cl	106	83
18	2-CH ₃	145	88
19	3-CH ₃	158	76
20	4-CH ₃	116	78

All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer.

1-(α -Aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides(I): α -Aryloxypropionyl hydrazines⁸ (0.01 M) and arylisothiocyanates (0.015 M) were refluxed gently in ethanol (30 ml) for 3 hrs, the solution

NOTES

cooled and the solid obtained was filtered, washed and recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The compounds gave single spots in tlc. IR : 3300-3400 cm^{-1} (ν CO.NH), 1220-1230 cm^{-1} (ν C-O-C), 1160-1180 cm^{-1} (ν C=S) and 750-755 cm^{-1} (ν C-Cl).

3-(α -Aryloxyethyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles^o(II): 1-(α -Aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazide (0.015 M) was refluxed in sodium hydroxide (35 ml, 8%) for 3 hrs, cooled and poured into large excess of water and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave a white solid which was washed and recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The compounds thus obtained gave single spots in tlc. IR : 3250-3350 cm^{-1} (ν NH), 1585-1600 cm^{-1} (ν C=N), 1225-1230 cm^{-1} (ν C-O-C-) and 1160-1170 cm^{-1} (ν C=S).

2-Arylamino-5-(α -aryloxyethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles^o(III): 1-(α -Aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazide (0.01 M) was dissolved with cooling in conc. sulfuric acid (10 ml) and stirred well. The solution was left at room temperature for 2 hrs, and poured over crushed ice. It was diluted with water (50 ml) and filtered. The residue was washed with water, recrystallised from dilute alcohol and gave single spots on tlc. IR : 3250-3300 cm^{-1} (ν NH), 1600-1615 cm^{-1} (ν C=N), 1230-1250 cm^{-1} (ν C-O-C-) and 695-710 cm^{-1} (ν -S-).

2-Arylamino-5-(α -aryloxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles^o(IV): Mercuric oxide (0.011 M) was added to a methanolic solution of 1-(α -aryloxypropionyl)-4-aryl-thiosemicarbazide (0.01 M) and the whole refluxed for 1 to 3 hrs. The precipitated mercuric sulfide was filtered and washed on the filter with hot methanol. The filtrate on cooling gave a precipitate which was recrystallised from ethanol and gave a single spot on tlc. IR : 3280-3340 cm^{-1} (ν NH), 1600-1630 cm^{-1} (ν C=N) and 1235-1260 cm^{-1} (ν C-O-C-).

Fungicidal screening: Fifteen compounds of Tables 1 and 2 were screened for their antifungal activity against *H. oryzae* and *A. brassicae* by agar plate technique¹⁰ at three different concentrations viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. All the compounds screened possessed moderate fungicidal activity against the above fungi.

The triazoles, though possessing higher antifungal activity than the parent thiosemicarbazides (I) and the corresponding oxadiazoles against *H. oryzae* display much less activity than the corresponding thiadiazoles. Against *A. brassicae*, the parent thiosemicarbazides are better fungicides than the corresponding triazoles which exhibit a little higher activity than the corresponding thiadiazoles and oxadiazole. Further the presence of chlorine atom ($R' = 4\text{-Cl}$) in the compounds increases the fungicidal activity over those having hydrogen or methyl group ($R' = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3$).

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References

1. R. P. BHAMARIA, R. A. BELLARE and C. V. DELIWALA, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1968, **6**, 62.
2. R. S. VERMA, K. C. GUPTA, AMARNATH and V. S. MISHRA, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1966, **64**, 13124e.
3. R. B. PATHAK, B. JAHAN and S. C. BAHRI, *J. Antibact. Antifung. Agents*, Japan, 1980, **8**, 12.
4. L. GSELL, and W. MEYER, *Ger. Offen.*, 2,739,084 (1978); *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **88**, 190844t.
5. G. L. MAHESHWARI, R. P. MAHESH and P. SINGH, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 549; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **83**, 193185j.
6. S. P. SUMAN and S. C. BAHRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 374.
7. I. CHIYOMARU, E. YOSHINAGA, H. KAWATA and H. ITO, *Japan*, 73 43, 615 (1973); *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, **81**, 59323h.
8. L. CONTI, *Bull. Sci. Fac. Chem. Ind. Bologna*, 1964, **22**, 13; *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **61**, 4253e.
9. AL. SILBERG and N. GOSMA, *Acad. rep. populare Romine Filiala Cluj, Studii Cercetari Univ.*, 1959, **10**, 161; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, **54**, 8795h, g, f.
10. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, **11**, 357.

Chemical and Pharmacological Studies on *Elaeocarpus ganitrus* Seeds

T. K. CHATTERJEE, A. K. DAS, S. K. CHOWDHURY,
S. GHOSH, A. BASAK and A. K. BARUA

Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, Calcutta-9
and

P. K. SARKAR

Department of Pharmacology, Medical College, Calcutta

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THE plant *Elaeocarpus ganitrus* Roxb. commonly known as *Rudraksha* in India belongs to the family Elaeocarpaceae¹. Chemical^{2,3} and pharmacological⁴⁻⁶ studies on this plant were reported earlier. The results of further chemical and pharmacological studies are presented in this paper.

Experimental

The crushed air-dried seeds of *E. ganitrus* (165 gms) were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) in a Soxhlet apparatus for 48 hrs and petroleum

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF OIL SEEDS AND OIL

Moisture %	8.87
Oil %	0.68
Colour of Oil	Pale Yellow
Consistency	Liquid
Refractive index at 30°	1.4650
Specific gravity at 32°	0.9300
Saponification value	176.0
Saponification equivalent	317.80
Iodine value	72.28
Acid value	34.89
Unsaponifiable Matter %	3.76